

SOME PROBLEMS OF LEARNING ENGLISH AND ALSO SOME POSITIVE SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

The article provides information about problems in learning English and their solutions. The main problems are lack of practicing and inability to form the speech correctly.

We know that nowadays, learning foreign languages demand for modern period. In our society has a proverb and this is that if people know modern languages, they will have golden opportunity for education purposes. Language is mirror of society. For example: All international conferences and agreements will be accomplished by only international and modern languages. Learning foreign language give a hand for learning not only, a new language but also, culture of this country. English is being international language. Such as, government of our country give lots of facilities in purpose of developing English. Learning language has some difficulties. Some aspects of England are the same with Uzbek but the grammar structure differs from Uzbek one. Even some grammar structures of English do not have Uzbek. For instance: article and this position will cause of some obstacles during the learning and we will solve this problems in our article.

First problem that is learners are spending much more time for learning theory and grammar (80%-90%) but they are not doing them in practice (10%-20%) as a result, they are not speaking fluently, representing their opinions clearly and they are doing this very badly. If learners want to solve this problem their practice percentage should be opposite to theory like this : theory and grammar (20%) practice (80%) .

Second problem is that people listen the conversation but they do not understand. But this aspect is crucial both conversation in English and also, replying answer to question. Misunderstanding by listening is common and famous issue, even know though people who know the grammar perfectly and have enough vocabulary bank but they face this type of matter. The problem is that people do not have specialized ability for listening (not determination of speech) . If people face the natural speech and also, natural speakers, they do not understand the whole meaning of this speech because they do not have enough topic vocabulary bank. In order to overcome this issue, learners should listen more and more

natural English speech and develop an English atmosphere. Listening materials should be both natural (mass media, lectures) and practical (movies, soap operas, and podcasts).

This problem is that people learn new vocabulary and they forget it regularly. For dealing with this problem, people try to learn this vocabulary correctly and should use it in conversation. For example: they make a sentence with new vocabulary. This condition will be taken enough consideration according to level of words and sophistication and they may make new sentences from 3 to 10 words. This method is easy and fast but much more effective way.

Final problem is related to the tenses and keeping words in our memory for a long time. Learning English tenses divide into 3 groups: 1) understand when the period will be used. 2) learning how to make sentence scheme with period. 3) making sentences with given period.

As a result, students use them not only during the making sentence, but also may use in their lives. Also, students think more and more time during the making sentence and they do not find out essential words easily and this is also a problem. But solving this problem, students should make sentence immediately when they learn new vocabularies after that they will give answer to any question automatically speaker. Because during the exercise these words vocabularies save for a long time in mind of learners.

Despite of having these problems, English is easier than other languages around the world. If people have strong determination and wish, they learn any languages easily and without difficulties. According to the statistics, a person broke a record which related to the learning English and this person learned English within 11 days. Scientists asked this person: "How did you learn this English language within 11 days?" This person answered that: "I gave up and removed all unnecessary things in my mind and took my all attention to only English consequently all of you saw my result". It has been seen that powerful wish and intend overcome all difficulties of during learning English language.

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